

IMMUNOLOGICAL AND CYTOKINE RESPONSE TO DIFFERENT TREATMENT STRATEGIES IN CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS

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Introduction. Chronic rhinosinusitis is associated with persistent local and systemic inflammation involving humoral immune disturbances and increased production of pro-inflammatory and type 2 cytokines. Evaluation of immunoglobulins and cytokines may provide additional information on the biological effectiveness of treatment.

Objective. To evaluate changes in immunoglobulin and cytokine levels following different comprehensive treatment strategies in patients with CRS.

Materials and Methods. A total of 110 patients with CRS were included in the study. Group A (n=40) received standard medical therapy; Group B (n=34) underwent FESS followed by standard therapy; and Group C (n=36) received FESS, standard therapy, and Derinat. Serum IgA, IgG, IgE, IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α , and IL-13 levels were measured before and after treatment.

Results. In Group A, immunological changes were limited: IgE decreased from 160 \pm 14 to 138 \pm 11 IU/mL ($p>0.05$), while cytokine levels decreased by approximately 1.1–1.2-fold. In Group B, IgE decreased from 170 \pm 15 to 104 \pm 9 IU/mL ($p<0.001$), accompanied by a 1.4–1.5-fold reduction in pro-inflammatory cytokines. The most substantial changes were observed in Group C. IgE decreased from 182 \pm 16 to 84 \pm 7 IU/mL ($p<0.001$), IgA from 15.7 \pm 0.7 to 9.9 \pm 0.3 g/L ($p<0.001$), and IgG from 4.8 \pm 0.3 to 2.3 \pm 0.1 g/L ($p<0.01$). In the same group, IL-1 β decreased from 8.0 \pm 0.6 to 4.6 \pm 0.3 pg/mL, IL-6 from 17.2 \pm 2.4 to 8.9 \pm 0.8 pg/mL, TNF- α from 16.1 \pm 2.7 to 7.9 \pm 0.9 pg/mL, and IL-13 from 4.7 \pm 0.4 to 2.4 \pm 0.2 pg/mL (all $p<0.001$).

Conclusion. FESS combined with standard therapy and Derinat was associated with the most pronounced reduction in humoral immune activity and pro-inflammatory cytokine production. This approach may provide enhanced control of inflammatory and type 2 immune mechanisms in patients with CRS.